

README — Supplementary Materials

This document describes the contents and intended use of the supplementary materials associated with the manuscript “Proposal of a Web Page Adaptation Model for Older Adults”.

Overview

The main manuscript references three appendices that may be hosted externally (e.g., via a Zenodo record) to reduce page count. These materials provide the full formal definitions and implementation-level details that complement the core contribution described in the paper.

Contents

- Appendix 1 — Data type definitions: complete list of data types used across the four profiles and metamodel instantiations.
- Appendix 2 — Primitives and rule examples: examples of adaptation primitives and representative ECA rules that invoke them.
- Appendix 3 — Runtime rule selection and execution pseudocode: full pseudocode of the event processing, rule filtering, ordering, guardrail checks, conservative collision handling, incremental profile update, and trace logging.
- Appendix 4 — Explanatory video on how OAWebAdapt works.

Suggested file layout in the archive

The archive may contain one file per appendix (PDF):

README.pdf

Appendix1_DataTypes.pdf

Appendix2_Primitives_and_Rules.pdf

Appendix3_Runtime_Pseudocode.pdf

Appendix3_video.mp4

How to cite

If these materials are deposited in Zenodo, cite the Zenodo record DOI in addition to the main article. For reproducibility, prefer citing the version-specific DOI (e.g., v1.0). Zenodo also provides a concept DOI that always points to the latest version.

Citation template (BibTeX) (replace placeholders with the actual Zenodo DOI and author list):

```
@misc{supplementary_zenodo_2026,  
  author = {<Authors>},  
  title = {Supplementary Material for:  
  Proposal of a Web Page Adaptation Model for Older Adults},  
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  url = {https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.<record_id>}  
}
```

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